

Potentiometric Studies of Acetylacetonanthranilic Acid (Schiff Base) Complexes of Nickel (II)

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Received 22 September, 1970 Revised MSS received 7 June, 1971

Acetylacetonone and anthranilic acid have been condensed to synthesise the Schiff base (abbr. H_2AA) and Metal complexes of nickel (II) with this base (ligand) have been studied potentiometrically. The dissociation constants of the ligand have been determined by interpolation at half n values and also by Algebraic-Method. The values are found to be 4.85 and 8.25 at 30° . The stability constants k_1 and k_2 of the metal complexes have been determined by adopting the Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method and their values are found to be 4.11 ($\log k_1$) and 2.29 ($\log k_2$) at 30° . In these complexes, 1:1 and 1:2 metal-ligand stoichiometry is suggested.

The most significant complexes of β -diketones are of the types (I) and (II) in which R, M and B represent generalised nitrogen, metal ion and bridging group substituents respectively.

In the present investigation Schiff base complexes having slightly different structural type (III) have been studied.

A survey of the literature shows that no systematic studies have been carried out on the stability and composition of acetylacetonanthranilic acid complexes of nickel (II) which appear akin to extensively studied salicylaldehyde complexes¹. In the present investigation the Calvin and Melchior's extension² of Bjerrum's method has been applied to determine the step-wise metal-ligand stability constants of the complexes. The measurements were carried out in 50 per cent dioxan as the reagent and the metal complexes are insoluble in water.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals were of the reagent grade quality and were further purified where necessary. Their solutions were prepared in 50% dioxan. A stock solution of ligand was standardised by potentiometric titration. The nickel nitrate solution was standardised by usual method³. Standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide was prepared³ and its solution in 50% dioxan was used as a titrant.

Preparation of the Schiff base: To freshly distilled acetylacetone (2.0 ml), anthranilic acid (2.6 g.) solution in hot ethanol was gradually added with stirring. Piperidine (3-4 drops) was used as a condensing agent. The mixture was refluxed on a waterbath for nearly an hour when a transparent yellow solution was obtained. Having allowed to cool, methanol was added and the solution was left overnight in a refrigerator for crystallisation. Fine shining yellow crystals of the Schiff base were obtained which were separated, recrystallised from methanol and preserved in a vacuum desiccator. Yield, 2.0 g., m.p., 156°; Found : C, 65.61; H, 5.82; N, 6.25; Calc. for $C_{12}H_{13}NO_3$: C, 65.75; H, 5.93; N, 6.36%.

A Cambridge bench pattern (null deflection type) pH meter with a wide range glass electrode in conjunction with a calomel electrode was used and calibrated at two pH values : at pH 4.01 with potassium hydrogen phthalate and at pH 7.0 with potassium hydrogen phosphate and sodium hydroxide buffers. All titrations were performed in a 250 ml beaker,

FIG 1 FORMATION CURVE OF PROTON-LIGAND SYSTEM OF H_2AA

equipped with a stirrer and in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The measurements were made at 30° and in ionic medium comprised of 0.1 M KNO_3 . The experimental method consisted of the potentiometric titrations of ligand in the absence and in the presence of nickel (II). Results obtained have been shown in figures 1-4.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dissociation constants: The ligand is a biprotic tridentate containing a carboxylic, an enolic hydroxyl and an imino group. The dissociation constants of the ligand have been calculated by the method used by S. Chaberek and A. E. Martell⁴. The values of \bar{n} i.e. the average number of protons attached per ligand ion, at various pH values have been calculated from the ligand titration curve.

The formation curve (Fig. 1) of the proton ligand system is found to be between 0 to 2 in \bar{n} scale which naturally denotes that two dissociations are possible in this case. The values of the dissociation constants were determined by the simple method of interpolation at half \bar{n} values and by the algebraic method⁴. Results obtained are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Dissociation constants (H_2AA)

Temp. = 30°

 $\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$

Methods	pK_1	pK_2
Interpolation at half \bar{n} values	4.85	8.25
Algebraic method	4.85	8.25

It is interesting to mention here that in the case of ligand titration, colour changes were observed as shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Change of colour intensity of H_2AA

pH	Colour
4.0-6.0	Colourless to faint yellow
6.1-8.3	Faint yellow to pale yellow
8.4 and above	Deep yellow

A change of colour from colourless to faint yellow is observed nearly at pH 4.5 at which \bar{n} is approximately 1.5. Colour also changes from faint yellow to pale yellow at pH 8.0 at which \bar{n} is approximately 0.5. This shows that the transition from H_2AA species to HAA^- and then from HAA^- species to AA^{-2} take place in solution.

FIG 2 POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF H_2AA IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF $Ni(II)$ WITH 0.1 M NaOH

Metal-ligand Stability Constants : The Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method has been used to calculate the stability constants of complexes from potentiometric titration data. The evaluation of \bar{n} was made from Fig. 2. At any pH the horizontal distance between curves I and II measures quite accurately the additional base consumed or the total number of moles of AA^{-2} complexed. This number divided by total nickel concentration is \bar{n} . At any pH, AA^{-2} was calculated as

$$[AA^{-2}] = \frac{[H_2AA]_{\text{Total}} - [NiAA] - 2[Ni(AA)_2^{-2}]}{\frac{[H^+]^2}{K_1 K_2} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_2} + 1}$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the first and second dissociation constants of H_2AA .

FIG. 3. PLOT OF \bar{n} AS FUNCTION OF $-\log [AA^{-2}]$

Fig. 3 represents the plot of \bar{n} against $-\log(AA^{-2})$. The approximate values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ were read directly from the graph at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively and their refinement was made by the following methods :

- (a) Bjerrum's method of successive approximation⁵.
- (b) Convergence formula of Schroder for successive approximation⁶.

The values obtained have been given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Methods	$\log k_1$	$\log k_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Extension of Bjerrum's method	4.11	2.29	6.40
Bjerrum's method of successive approximation	4.08	2.32	6.40
Schroder's convergence formula	4.08	2.32	6.40
Mean	4.09	2.31	6.40

It is apparent from the table that the direct expressions

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{[L]_{\bar{n}=0.5}} - \frac{3}{[L]_{\bar{n}=1.5}} \quad \& \quad k_2 = \frac{1}{[L]_{\bar{n}=1.5}} - \frac{3}{[L]_{\bar{n}=0.5}}$$

given by Schroder for the convergence values of successive approximations as modification of M.S.A., are strictly followed by our data and divergence of the convergence formula is noted. This method is recent and directly gives the true values of successive stability constants.

FIG 4 POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF H_2AA IN PRESENCE AND ABSENCE OF NICKEL (II), WITH 0.1M NaOH

Curve IV—12 ml of 0.05M H_2AA +4 ml of 0.05M $Ni(NO_3)_2$ +4 ml of 1M KNO_3 +20 ml 50% dioxane.

Curve I—4 ml of 0.05M H_2AA +4 ml of 1M KNO_3 +32 ml 50% dioxane.

Curve II—4 ml of 0.05M H_2AA +4 ml of 0.05M $Ni(NO_3)_2$ +4 ml of 1M KNO_3 +28 ml 50% dioxane.

Curve III—8 ml of 0.05M H_2AA +4 ml of 0.05M $Ni(NO_3)_2$ +4 ml of 1M KNO_3 +24 ml 50% dioxane.

Composition : In Fig. 4 the curve I represents the pH titration between H_2AA and alkali in absence of metal and shows two inflections at one and two moles of NaOH per mole of ligand; thus suggesting that two protons respectively from $-COOH$ and $-OH$ groups are replaced by sodium. The shape of the titration curve II is greatly changed in presence of equimolecular concentration of nickel ion. A considerable lowering in buffer region is noticed and two inflections at 2 and 3 moles of NaOH per mole of ligand are observed. The occurrence of first inflection at 2 moles of NaOH in place of one mole indicates the extra consumption of one mole of NaOH due to liberation of H^+ from $-OH$ group also at lower pH value due to complexation.

The liberation of protons take place simultaneously from $-COOH$ and $-OH$ groups in the presence of metal ion and so overlapping curve for these two is obtained in the form

of one inflection. This inflection shows the formation of 1 : 1 complex according to the following equation

The inflection at 3 moles of NaOH per mole of ligand further shows the consumption of one additional mole of NaOH. This inflection which starts from pH 8.8 suggests that the disproportion of the 1 : 1 complex takes place into 1 : 2 complex and half of the nickel precipitates as $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$. This reaction may be represented as follows :

When two moles of ligand are added to a single mole of nickel (Curve III) the curve shows only one inflection at 4 moles of base, which corresponds to the replacement of the carboxylic and enolic protons as a result of the formation of 1 : 2 complex. The titration of solution containing metal and ligand in the ratio of 1 : 3 (Curve III) yields inflections at 5 and 6 moles of base corresponding to the replacement of carboxylic and enolic protons, and one enolic proton, revealing the formation of 1 : 2 complex. Thus the present investigation reveals that the interaction between nickel (II) and ligand gives 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The values of $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ have been found to be 4.09 and 2.31.

The authors acknowledge their grateful thanks to Prof. R. C. Kapoor for providing laboratory facilities and to Dr. J. P. Saxena for valuable suggestions.

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